

The Implication of Blockchain Technology in the Emission Trading Scheme of Gujarat

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1 Introduction

In June 2019, the pilot emission trading program was launched in Surat, followed by Ahmedabad in May 2021 and Ludhiana in June 2021. Contrary to the cap-and-trade schemes all around the world, these programs aim to cut Suspended Particulate Matters (SPM)- one of the causes of heart disease, stroke, diabetes, etc..

The “Cap-and-Trade Scheme”- the government imposes limits on particle emissions and allows industries to buy and sell permits to stay below the threshold (McIntyre, 2019; Raghavan, 2019; Singh, 2019; Tripathi, 2019)- is flexible and reduces emissions by 24% compared to other plants under the “control-and-control” rule- which has led to high levels of disobedience and a lack of quality information.

After the release of Nakamoto (2008), several authors proposed ideas on the application of block-chain in different areas including climate change. This dissertation explores the implications of blockchain technology in Surat’s program. The research questions are as follows::

- What are the challenges the current scheme has?
- How the blockchain technology can help in overcoming those challenges?
- Which blockchain model is the best fitted to the current scheme?

In this dissertation, Surat’s scheme is studied for two reasons: (i) Surat’s scheme is the first scheme in India and Ahmedabad’s scheme and Ludhiana’s scheme are just replication; (ii) In comparison to the other jurisdiction’s scheme, more information and data are available for Surat’s scheme. In addition to this, the focus is more on the policy aspect of the solution provided and the technological aspect will remain out of the scope. In this dissertation, “Emission Trading Scheme”, “ETS”, “Scheme”, “System” and “Model” are words used interchangeably. Likewise the words “Permit”, “Licence” and “Allowance” would be used interchangeably.

In the next section, previous similar works are explored; in the third section, an analysis of the current scheme is done and challenges in the current model are identified; how the blockchain technology can be useful in emission trading schemes is discussed in the fourth section; in the fifth section a new blockchain-enabled model for Surat’s emission trading is proposed and the conclusion is given in the last section.

2 Review of Literature

The rise of the Blockchain has had a profound effect on evolution and the advancement of sustainable practices, especially in emission trading.

Perino and Willner (2016) discuss the EU-ETS alternatives to postpone the issuance of new allowances in case there is a surplus in the market to boost the price of the allowances. Perthuis (2011) proposed the creation of a central authority to control the provision of allowances in order to keep the price of allowances stable.

Wood and Jotzo (2009) examine the idea of implementing a carbon floor price to establish a minimum price of credits. To eliminate an oversupply of allowances and huge profitability, Woerdman, Couwenberg, and Nentjes (2009) suggest various allowance allocation approaches that involve amending the pre-allocation based on the enterprises’ actual output and carbon intensity. The intent of all of these solutions is to restrict the price of the allowance by limiting supply or forcing a minimum price; the end goal is to raise the global price of the allowance to a set level, making the purchase of extra allowances a less appealing alternative. However,

these solutions will not be able to fulfil their full potential, while the integrity of all policies remains a challenge.

Pan et al. (2019) explore how various features of blockchain technology help corporates as well as individuals in emission trading but they failed in giving trading mechanisms.

Saraji and Borowczak (2021)- using a tokenization mechanism- propose a Carbon Credit Ecosystem to create a Carbon Credit Ecosystem on Blockchain to bring more liquidity, transparency, accessibility, and standardization to carbon markets. Khaqqi et al. (2018) construct a blockchain-enabled reputation-based emission trading system (BCRB) with the intention of minimizing fraud and strengthening emission trading management. Contrary to the conventional mechanisms, “Market Segmentation” and “Priority-Value Order” are considered in trade execution. Access to the bids/offers of any firm depends on their market segment. Khaqqi et al. (2018) also compared BCRB with the standard ETS and concluded that BCRB is better in terms of environmental performance and political acceptance but the feasibility of implementing both models is more or less the same. The framework, on the other hand, does not specify where the reputation comes from, and the priority value does not describe the transaction. Dash, Rawat, and Ranjan (2019) try to explore the applicability of the same model in Surat’s scheme but failed to give any new conclusion.

Sadawi et al. (2021) tries to incorporate all the emission trading activities with blockchain technology and gives a comprehensive and hierarchical blockchain for emission trading system (CHBETS). This framework addresses carbon budget manipulation, corruption, non transparency, and lack of conviction, as well as the complexity of the allowance allocation process, the dearth of emission traceability assessments, the non-unification of the emission trading market, high transaction costs, and unfair trading. However, the framework only focuses on optimization of trading mechanisms and not on incentivizing firms to participate and innovate of emission-less manufacturing facilities.

3 Analysis of the Current Scheme

The Gujarat Pollution Control Board (GPCB) developed an emissions trading scheme with the help of a team of researchers to understand its impact on emissions, industry costs, and control costs.

Participants were chosen depending on the size of their chimneys - 24 inches diameter or larger - from a variety of industries such as textiles, chemicals, and sugar, and were scattered throughout an area of 50-30 square kilometres. At the beginning of each one-month compliance period, 80% of the total amount for that period is still distributed free of charge to all participating units based on industry emission sources, and the remaining 20% of permits are auctioned off during the first the compliance period. At that moment, participating units can buy and sell permits between themselves. The price cannot be more than ₹100 per kilogramme or lower than ₹5 per kilogramme. The permit holding limit was 150% of the initial allocation or 5% share of the total market capitalization and the sales limit was 90% of the initial share.

These transactions took place on the ETS-PM trading platform, which is hosted by the National Commodities and Derivatives Exchange e-Markets Limited (NeML). There were two different kinds of auctions. Every Tuesday between 3PM and 5 PM, participants in the Uniform Price Auction determine the week’s allowance price by bidding. Second, between Wednesday and Monday (2 PM to 5 PM), there is an ongoing market where members buy and sell allowances, with pricing set on Tuesday. ₹200 environmental damage compensation per kilogram is placed on top of each kilogram of emission in addition to the permits the unit has. Participants must

also make a “Environmental Damage Compensation Deposit”, which ranges from ₹2 lakh for small businesses to ₹3 lakh for medium businesses and ₹10 lakh for large businesses (Ghanekar, 2021). At the end of the trading period, the quantity of permits need to be at least equal to the the actual emission by the factory in order to comply. Therefore, after a trading period, the permissions will eventually be reissued. Each industry shall appoint a nodal representative who will be actively involved in monitoring CEMS data and trading of permits under the Emission Trading Scheme (ETS). Goel (2019) identifies the following challenges:

3.1 The transparent allocation of permits

To avoid allegations of corruption or bias and disputations over possible losses to the exchequer - such as the “2G License Scandal” - the government needs to increase revenue and avoid ambiguous allocation of permits. Although the auction based system guarantees transparency, the high price of permits may also cause larger industries to hoard allowances to cutting reducing their emissions which could adversely impact the economic competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

3.2 Balancing economic competitiveness with emissions reduction

The EU’s emissions trading scheme has has been criticised for over-allocating licences, which makes factories pay more readily for pollution. It will be easier for a large firm to invest in a capital-intensive technology and reduce its emission but not that much easy for an SME. A lower limit might harm the industrial state’s economic strength, while a high limit would postpone decarbonisation and diminish the program’s efficacy.

3.3 Extending the program to include high-polluting industries

The present pilot program hhas only targeted a few sectors, but it has to be expanded to include more sectors in order to successfully combat air pollution. The system must be flexible to accommodate other locations. Another issue is that most regulations in the existing system are written taking into account physical examination by a government inspector but the rules are almost non-existent for this new technology.

3.4 Preventing the export of polluting activities to unregulated jurisdictions

The transfer of polluting activities from Surat to uncontrolled cities is the greatest danger of adopting the cap-and-trade scheme. This would obscure the program’s success, as a reduction in one area might lead to greater in emissions in another. Although the cap-and-trade programme has the potential to be a useful instrument in the battle against industrial air pollution, its adoption in India’s complicated political environment is notoriously tricky.

4 Analysis of Blockchain Technology as a Solution

A blockchain is made up of a collection of blocks. tied together in a series. If the blockchain is similar a ledger book, a block can be equated to a page in the book; it records a collection

of events that occur during a specific time period. The hash of a block is generated using the contents of that block.

This hash will then be used as one of the values in the next block. Any modification in the value of a block will result in an unexpected change in the hash. As a result, if a modification in the prior block is approved and regarded acceptable, all subsequent blocks must be regenerated to reflect that single change. Access to the blockchain will be consistent and irrevocable in this fashion. Each ledger copy with any node is same to the others. The only occurrences that are considered valid are those that are accepted by the majority. A consensus algorithm is used to achieve this. It also shifts confidence away from central authorities like governments, banks, and attorneys and toward the participants directly. Decentralization, distribution, security, transparency, automation, traceability, and privacy are unique characteristics of the blockchain architecture.

4.1 Smart Contracts

Smart contracts have been the most important technologies since the advent of blockchain, which adds a high degree of flexibility to standard transactions. Smart contracts, in essence, are virtual versions of real-world contracts that bind two or more parties. A smart contract can be defined as “a software program that adds layers of information onto the transactions being executed on a blockchain” (Sadiku, Eze, and Musa, 2018). As a result, the functions, and tasks normally controlled or performed by a centralized power, middlemen, or third - party like attorneys or carbon dealers have now been shifted to the blockchain. Clearly, and since smart contracts remain on an immutable blockchain, they can provide the necessary protection to operate at a higher level than those functions performed under conventional contract regulations.

4.2 Categories of Blockchain

Blockchain is categorized as public, private, and consortium access based on proprietary characteristics and access management. The type of blockchain used is typically determined by the application’s architecture and needs.

- **Public:**

It’s a permissionless blockchain with public transactions but anonymous participants. Anyone may utilise block explorers on the public blockchain, which is an open source ledger found on the internet to check out and evaluate what is being done.

- **Private:**

is a permissioned blockchain that describes a registry of licensed users with specific operating features within the network. Ownership of this type is controlled by a single entity and is used by organisations to document activities or assets and distribute data to a restricted number of users.

- **Federated or Consortium or Hybrid or Semi-Private:** this blockchain is a combination of the public and private blockchain. It is open to the public and restricted to a single privileged node, which is generally a group of organisations. Authorized gatekeepers, rather than unidentified random miners, validate transactions in this sort of blockchain.

5 Proposed Model

The proposed model is fundamentally similar the current scheme, however, some components from Khaqqi et al. (2018) and Sadawi et al. (2021) are included in the model to eliminate or limit the challenges.

5.1 Components of the Model

The proposed model is shown in Figure 1. The model has mainly four participants: the first is “Authority”- which is shown at the top and which is responsible for a creation & enforcement of the scheme and issuance & distribution of the allowances (GPCB in our case); the second is “Firm” which is responsible in reporting the emission, trading of the emission allowances and surrendering the balance emission allowances; the third is “Bank” which is responsible for accepting the allowance as a deposit from one firm and lending it to another firm; and the last is “Auditor” who works very closely with the Carbon Asset Management System (CAMS).

Figure 1: Proposed Model

The proposed model has three levels of hierarchy. Upper application -level public blockchain which deals with auctioning, trading, off-setting, surrendering and Carbon Asset Management (CAM) activities. This level has four smart contracts: allowance issuance & distribution, asset management, allowance trading, and allowance reporting & surrender. Usage of Multichain, Ethereum or a new dedicated blockchain is recommended as transactions of the auction, trading, off-setting and surrendering should be transparent and traceable. Lower measurement -level permissioned blockchain which handles the measurement of emission related data collected by the Continuous Emission Monitoring System (CEMS) installed in the emission generating units and matched with the allowances that a firm already has. Blockchain like Hyperledger fabric or Hyperledger composers is recommended to maintain the operational privacy of the participating firms. The lower level is supported by only one smart contract to match emission with allowance. Cross transfer level which connects the lower level with the upper level and manages the transmission of data across the blockchains. Polkadot Protocol, Interledger Protocol or Hyperledger Grid can be used in the middle level for interoperability of both the blockchains.

Scope of the scheme refers to the sector (i.e. textiles, chemicals and sugar), gases (i.e. SPM), entities (i.e. industrial units with chimneys having a diameter of 24 inches or more) and jurisdictions (i.e. Surat) covered under the scheme. In the current scheme, the floor price is ₹5 per kilogram and the ceiling price is ₹100 per kilogram which is an example of a price control. Authority decides the upper limit of the emission- cap- for a specified period after considering the scope of the scheme, price controls, compliance & oversight and consultation with the stakeholders (nodal representatives from each industry in our case).

Carbon Asset Management System (CAMS) is one of the unique and important components of a model that allows for the recording, measurement, control, and reporting of issued carbon permits, investments undertaken, capital spending, emission offsets, and green energy consumption. In addition, the use of blockchain helps improve corporate governance and national standards through the development of a carbon credit or reputation-based trading system. Any highlighted action that has been encoded by the parties in the smart contract, such as changes in production circumstances, abuse of energy, altered crude ingredients, or variation in emission outcomes, may be dealt with by the asset management system. Banks also interact with the CAMS to lend or take deposits from the participants. The advantage of blockchain technology is that, while lending (or accepting deposits) bank knows the fund requirements and credit rating of the borrower but the bank can not identify which participant is borrowing. This will eliminate the possibility of favoured lending. At the end of each quarter, the allowance will be repaid with the interest to the bank.

With an offset mechanism- which is not present in the current scheme- participating firms can get credit from their green initiatives in the uncovered sectors which reduces the emission of the same gas located in the same jurisdiction. There would be a ceiling for the offset transactions. This gives flexibility which may encourage firms not to set up plants elsewhere and export the pollution.

The requirement for the Environmental Damage Compensation Deposit and the Environmental Damage Compensation will remain the same as the current scheme in the new model.

5.2 Reputation Based Trading Mechanism

The trading mechanism under the reputation-based model is shown in Figure 2. The trading procedure is divided into three stages, viz. "Bids/Offer collection", "Bids/Offer sorting" and "Bids/Offer Matching". Buyers/Sellers can collect offers/bids based only on their market

Figure 2: Trading Procedure

segmentation. Market segmentation determines the access of bids/offers to the traders which depend on their reputation i.e. the higher the reputation, higher the market access, and vice versa as shown in Figure 3. In the second stage, contrary to the conventional model, offers are sorted based on the priority which is the function of the sellers' reputation. The left side of Figure 4 shows offer made by the seller with a higher reputation has higher priority and vice versa. Sorting of bids is based on their relative price- same as the conventional model i.e. higher the bid price, higher the priority and vice versa as indicated on the right side of Figure 4. In the third stage, bids and offers are matched based on visibility and priority. In this stage, participants are further divided into two categories: (i) Active participants- who are looking for bids/offers actively and willing to trade at any price (ii) Passive participants- who are willing to trade on specified (or better than specified) bid/offer price but not otherwise. The quantity of emission permits demanded by an active buyer is fulfilled by the most prioritised offers available to her based on her market access, while the quantity of emission permits demanded by

Figure 3: Market Segmentation

Figure 4: Bids/Offers Sorting

a passive buyer is fulfilled by the most prioritised offer below the specified bid price available to her based on her market access. Quantity supplied by an active seller is sold on the highest bid price available to her as per her market segment, while for a passive seller the transaction is done on the highest price available to her above the specified offer price. Reputation-based market segmentation and offer prioritisation ensures participants weigh more on the adoption of long-term abatement technology rather than relying on the emission market.

6 Conclusion

Indian cities contain some of the most dangerous air in the world, and 8 out of 10 Indians inhale poisonous air, which killed 1.24 million people in 2017 – more than TB, diarrhoea, pneumonia, and malaria combined (Tripathi, 2019). Though emission trading scheme for the SPM

is more effective than the command-and-control scheme, it suffers from certain challenges. The challenges like transparent allocation of the permits, balancing economic competitiveness with emissions reduction, expanding the program to highly polluted sectors and preventing the transfer of polluting activities to unregulated areas is being discussed. This answers to the first research question (See Section 3). Analysis of the characteristics, architecture and types which can help overcome some of the challenges is done (See Section 4) and tried to find an answer for our second research question.

After understanding the current scheme and blockchain technology, a model is proposed (See Section 5). As the model is not changed fundamentally and the device of emission monitoring (i.e. CEMS) will also remain the same in the proposed model, it will take lesser effort from the administrative aspects to modify the model. Though the technology suggested in the model is more advanced, it seems less feasible in the short term, but after two or three mock trading periods with the new model, we can get a better idea. On the financial side, the initial investment is higher but the successful implementation also guarantees a higher return in the form of better air quality. Three levels of blockchain, CAMS and reputation-based trading is the backbone of the proposed model which ensures transparency as well as privacy at the same time.

Though it has been more than a decade since the first paper on blockchain technology was published by Nakamoto (2008), there is still very less awareness of this technology. Its association with cryptocurrency which is mostly used for speculative activities- creates more confusion about the technology's legal status. Because of these reasons, it may create resistance from the stakeholders for the adoption.

This dissertation mostly focuses on the policy aspect of the study, there is a scope for the research on technological aspects of the same model. Without any empirical study these questions remain: will the proposed model balance economic competitiveness with emission reduction? Is it possible to expand the proposed model to other sectors? And how can the problem of export of pollution activities be tackled?

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